

Public Policy for the Management of Agricultural Industrialization in the District of Motupe

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to analyze the perception of the implementation of the Public Policy for the management of agricultural industrialization in the district of Motupe. It used a qualitative methodology, grounded theory design, having as a study scenario agroindustrial enterprises of the district of Motupe. The data collection technique was the interview, and the instrument was the interview guide, having as participants authorities of the District Municipality of Motupe, Provincial Municipality of Lambayeque, Regional Government of Lambayeque, as well as representatives of the Board of Irrigators of Motupe, workers and officials of the agroindustrial enterprises located in the district of Motupe. The results were that the perception is significant in that there are currently no public policies in the

agroindustrial sector that reflect the real need to improve the conditions of this sector. Finally, it concluded that the implementation of territorial policies in the agroindustry of the district of Motupe has a significant benefit since there are no public policies according to the needs of the sector under study.

Keywords: Public policies; Agribusiness sector; Perception.

Introduction

The topic of study is focused on public management, which arises from the need presented by companies or entrepreneurs to know strategies that allow them to improve the development of their operations and, more importantly, to find the best way to use the resources that are essential for the growth or entrepreneurship of new companies. This is related to the government's involvement through public investments, which allow it to reach various regions of the national environment and turn them into beneficiaries of projects carried out in their use (Huacchillo et al., 2020).

The agricultural sector is one of the most important in all countries mainly because it is linked to food security, which is addressed in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In addition, agriculture is an economic activity that facilitates mechanisms for eliminating hunger in mainly vulnerable populations; global development policies currently focus on reducing food loss and waste to combat malnutrition (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2019).

Scientific studies carried out by the United Nations have shown that the rate of reduction of hunger is slow, which means that by 2030 the goal of zero hunger will not be achieved; because of this situation, governments worldwide have been implementing strategies through public policies that address issues of agriculture, industrialization and environmental care, based on planning with a territorial approach developed in each country. The hunger problem is addressed through improvements in the agrifood system, promoting the industrialization of agriculture and seeking a sustained increase in production (United Nations, 2020).

The increase in the demand for food is due to the demographic increase, a factor that has impacted the development of agriculture; likewise, with the increase in population comes the need for housing and, consequently, the implementation of more real estate projects; This problem has caused the need to expand the agricultural frontier, which is currently decreasing due to the development of real estate projects, reducing the areas suitable for cultivation, leading to the generation of another problem such as forest deforestation, developing agriculture in unsuitable soils and degrading soil quality (Ziegler et al., 2020).

In Peru, according to the Central Reserve Bank of Peru (2020), agriculture is one of the main economic activities; however, in the last 50 years, it has undergone elemental changes, mainly due to the agrarian reform implemented by the government of President Juan Velasco Alvarado in 1969-1976, which led to a shift from agriculture concentrated in haciendas to smallholdings; With the distribution of land, each agrarian worker received a small plot of land, which caused large-scale agriculture to become subsistence agriculture, slowing the development of this activity. Nevertheless, according to a report by the Central Reserve Bank of Peru (2020), agroindustrial production grew by 6.6% (Cabel, 2020).

Currently, agriculture is the main source of income in the country since approximately 2.3 million families depend on it, representing 34% of Peruvian families and contributing 7.6% to the gross domestic product. Moreover, agro-exports have grown by 14.5% annually since 2000 and have been boosted by signing free trade agreements (Bula, 2020).

At the national level, the extension of agricultural land amounts to 2.5 million hectares, 84% of which is used for producing transitory crops, such as rice (19%) and hard yellow corn (14%). Although forestry extension is oriented toward producing renewable products, there are 78.8 million hectares of land with forestry potential, made up of natural forests (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2019).

The district of Motupe in the province of Lambayeque, a department of the same name, is characterized by the development of agriculture as the main economic activity, based mainly on fruit production. At present, in the territory of the district, there are agro-industrial companies that plant and process mainly the mango product, among which, Plantaciones del Sol SAC, Agroindustrial Damper, Agroindustria Frutos de Oro SAC, and others; however, although with the implementation of the Olmos irrigation project, the district of Motupe has been able to take advantage of water resources, there is still no emphasis on agroindustrial development because there is no adequate irrigation infrastructure (canals, reservoirs) to ensure the sustainability of the agricultural activity. There is also a lack of implementation of public policies related to this sector; although there is indeed a range of public policies designed, to date, their implementation has not been seen, starting with the national agricultural policy, which aims to improve income levels and the quality of life of farmers, as well as increase the productivity of the sector, This policy also addresses the issue of environmentally responsible agroindustry that seeks to avoid damaging the forests by expanding the agricultural frontier and contributing to guaranteeing food security, but in the department of Lambayeque, mainly in the district of Motupe and neighboring districts, there has been a clear process of deforestation of the dry forest to gain farmland, which is why there are projections that in approximately 10 years Lambayeque and part of Piura will lose their dry forest.

Literature review

Industrial sector

According to Isem and Galati (2015), the industrial sector performs according to the economic model, and based on what has been evidenced in the industrial development of capitalist countries, urban development is promoted by encouraging economic variables such as income at the macroeconomic level. However, public and private investment, consumption and technology development through research are also encouraged. Traditional means of production, combined with a good institutional environment, generate optimal conditions for territorial development.

Agricultural policies

From the outset, agricultural policies have focused on the need to promote technology to improve the productivity of the land and produce greater quantities to meet the growing population's food needs. The social purpose of agriculture is based on the relationship between the state and rural society's relationship. For the classical school of economic thought (p.152).

Agricultural policies in Peru allow farmers to increase their income and quality of life, mainly through family farming, while improving their productivity through social inclusion and economic improvements in rural communities (Castillo et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, as in many other countries, agriculture plays an important role in the economy because it is the second largest source of income and formal employment, in which agriculture produces one of every four jobs (Castillo et al., 2020).

According to Hecló & Wildavsky (1974), public policy is the set of actions that governments implement to develop the implementation of the strategic route; with previous experiences, Meny & Thoening (1992) define it as the action that authorities must execute in favor of society based on existing problems. Finally, with an approach closer to what is currently being developed, the author's Muller & Surel (1998) define public policy as a process through which action programs are developed and executed in agreement among all development agents related to the fulfillment of society's development objectives.

The national agricultural policy highlights a solution to poverty, but the improvement indicators do not show it because these producers are vulnerable to the management of the governors of change, who promote projects and programs for the most organized producers with a focus on technical assistance and neglect the less organized ones. Producers in rural areas lack financing for this type of activity, and in this regard, Elver (2018) argues that the ineffectiveness of non-family farming projects is due to poorly established policies that only target legally recognized companies. What proves that programs lack effectiveness is that they are often poorly implemented without sustained support.

As public policies are developed, there is a growing need to focus on ensuring the advancement of agriculture, so each country's government defines these policies to achieve the sustainable development goals of zero hunger, food security and poverty eradication. Initial steps should include identifying public problems and products with the greatest production problems, such as the maize, which requires large tracts of land for global cultivation and is grown in most countries, which makes the labyrinth a good example for sectoral competition analysis. However, it should be noted that competition should be examined from all angles, not only from the perspective of supply and demand. Despite ideal climatic conditions, labyrinth production in Latin America does not reflect economic efficiency because the only return on investment is achieved (Velásquez et al., 2020).

Agrarian policy approaches in Peru

MINAGRI (2016) designed and implemented multidisciplinary approaches to guide the intervention and implementation processes of the National Agricultural Policy in the context of sustainable development:

Human rights approach

Its objective is to identify and address discriminatory practices and unequal power distribution that impede development by analyzing the social and economic inequalities present in agricultural development. The State violates human rights when it fails to implement its public policies aimed at reducing poverty and hunger, as well as the inclusion of social and economic factors in agricultural plans and projects (Castillo et al., 2020).

Territorial approach

Since the territory is intimately related to the fundamental economic, productive, social, cultural, environmental and political activities of an agricultural community, it guides the formulation and development of development standards within the framework of participatory democracy. Lima's Centralism is the most obvious example of this, which continues to develop in the same way today. The government's success derives from its ability to unite the countryside and the cities (Castillo et al., 2020).

Sustainable development approach

The goal is to preserve the world through the intelligent use of natural resources while respecting the environment and the survivability of future generations. However, the development of sustainable food systems prioritizes human health, ecosystem viability, nutrition and climate change, and social justice (Caron et al., 2018).

Sustainable development

Analyzing the sustainable development from a theoretical point of view, it should be understood as a situational condition in which the need to improve the social, economic and environmental conditions of the population is realized, considering the development models of the territory, with the condition of adequate use of the resources and services provided by nature, always considering that the reality is changing; therefore planners should always perform trend analysis of the variables that according to the model of territory are of greater influence, which can be technological, cultural and economic. Furthermore, sustainable development is inclusive, seeking that all people have the same opportunity to develop and have a quality of life by providing public services appropriate to each of the existing needs (Xercavins et al., 2005).

Sustainable development requires other theories to establish policy implementation mechanisms. Among these theories is strategic planning, the reality of which in Peru is described by Guerra-García (2001) in “Towards a governmental strategic planning system for Peru”. He emphasized how disconnected Peru’s planning, programming and budgeting processes had become over time. This problem has persisted to this day. He makes several key suggestions about how planning and budgeting are closely related. The first is that planning is designed to anticipate potential outcomes and direct current choices to organize the desired future. The second states that planning should be comprehensive and use all necessary resources. Planning also connects the means with the goals to be achieved.

The theory of sustainable development is conceptualized based on the three pillars, economic, social and environmental, as stated by Reed (cited in Mesino, 2007, p. 117-119), economic development focuses on economic growth, the proper use of means of production from a productivity approach, however, the social component addresses the issue of welfare of the individual and society that focuses on providing quality of life, and finally, the environmental component promotes the proper use of natural resources, as well as mitigating the effects of climate change. In general, well-being seeks to ensure that society can develop.

The main objective of the national agricultural policy in Peru is to support and promote competitive and inclusive agricultural growth that benefits farmers and improves their quality of life and that of their respective communities. The six axes on which the policy was developed are human rights, social inclusion, sustainable development, gender, interculturality and territorial integrity. In order to design corrective measures, the human rights analysis focuses on identifying and analyzing social and economic inequalities in the agricultural sector, placing sufficient emphasis on developing agricultural infrastructure. According to the social inclusion analysis, the rural population in the highlands and páramo of the country lacks opportunities to develop the agricultural sector and is also isolated from development due to difficult connectivity with inadequate transportation routes. Finally, the idea of sustainable development proposes a rational use of resources, mainly soil and water, to contribute to sustainable food security.

Research method

This research employs a qualitative approach to demonstrate the objectives set. The participants were public officials from the District Municipality of Motupe, Provincial Municipality of Lambayeque, Regional Government of Lambayeque, and representatives of the Board of Irrigators of Motupe and officials of agroindustrial companies located in the district of Motupe. This research uses the purposive sampling method. The total number of participants was 7 officials, the information was collected through interviews and analyzed through descriptive analysis.

Results

Analyze the perception of implementing the PP for managing agricultural industrialization in the district of Motupe

From the interviewees' responses, it can be seen that the perception is significant in that there are currently no public policies in the agroindustrial sector that reflect the real need to improve the conditions of this sector.

Their perception is significant because, to date, there are no strategies to implement public policies aimed at the agroindustrial sector; moreover, they do not exist, and those that do exist are outdated. They are also unaware of all the existing regulations at the national level in the agroindustrial sector.

Diagnose the benefits that implementing territorial policies in the agroindustry of the district of Motupe will generate

The implementation of territorial policies in the agroindustry of the district of Motupe has an important benefit because there are no public policies according to the needs of the sector under study. Those interviewed say that there are no public policies in the agroindustrial sector; therefore, their implementation will generate great benefits that will improve the current deficient situation.

Therefore, implementation will be advantageous because there are no known strategies for implementing public policies in the agroindustrial sector.

Describe the existing national public policies in the agroindustrial sector in the department of Lambayeque

The interviewees consider that, within public policies, the Agrarian Law stands out. However, these policies are diverse and benefit the agroindustrial sector.

From the analysis, it can be concluded that existing public policies are not well defined by the authorities, or at least they are not efficiently aware of their purpose.

Evaluate the current situation of the agroindustrial sector in the district of Motupe

It is concluded that the current situation of the agroindustrial sector in the district of Motupe, according to the opinions of most of those interviewed, is deficient because in the last 5 years they have not been able to design public policies that benefit this sector, and if they do exist, they are distorted and do not allow for improvements. As a result, new public policies have not been implemented.

Discussion

Analyze the perception of the implementation of the PP for the management of agricultural industrialization in the district of Motupe

Most interviewees stated that the perception is significant because there are currently no public policies in the agroindustrial sector that reflect the real need to improve the conditions of this sector. Likewise, Arias and Preciado (2015), in their research in Colombia, pointed out that evidence of the reality of farmers in the context of the non-existent state policy that promotes development in this sector, which has not made any intervention to improve conditions, this reality is not alien throughout this part of the continent suffer from this problem. This is why, given the generation of social conflict due to the absence of communication between the State and the population, it is necessary to generate channels of dialogue, but mainly the development and implementation of public policies that give impetus to such an important and at the same time sensitive sector of the economy of a country (p. 113-118).

Diagnose the benefits that the implementation of territorial policies in the agroindustry of the district of Motupe will generate

Most of those interviewed stated that implementing territorial policies in the agroindustry of the Motupe district would be of significant benefit because there are deficient public policies that do not meet the needs of the sector under study. Therefore, Vega, Paredes and Almeida (2019), in their research, refer that, given this reality, the researchers propose that, via the State and the development and implementation of public policies, it is possible to stimulate the necessary conditions to achieve the objectives set out in the framework of the development of the sector (p. 334-337).

Describe the existing national public policies in the agroindustrial sector in the department of Lambayeque.

Most interviewees stated that existing public policies are not well defined by the authorities, or they are not efficiently aware of their purpose. According to Hecló & Wildavsky (1974), public policy is the set of actions that governments implement to develop the implementation of the strategic route; with previous experiences, Meny & Thoening (1992) define it as the action that authorities must execute in favor of society based on existing problems. With an approach closer to what is currently being developed, the authors Muller & Surel (1998) define public policy as a process through which concerted action programs are developed and executed by all development agents related to the fulfillment of society's development objectives. Furthermore, for the adequate analysis of public policies, the fulfillment of three conditions must be verified, and the first is the definition of objectives to achieve the desired future, the means and actions for policy implementation and the follow-up and monitoring for the analysis of results (Roth, 2008).

Evaluate the current situation of the agroindustrial sector in the district of Motupe

Most of the interviewees stated that the current situation of the agroindustrial sector in the district of Motupe is deficient because, in the last 5 years, they have not been able to design public policies that benefit this sector, and if they do exist, they are distorted and do not allow for improvements. This finding is consistent with the study by Castillo et al. (2020), who in their research referred that the effectiveness of the national agricultural policy in Peru identified that its purpose is to promote agricultural development from a sustainable and competitive approach that allows farmers to improve their quality of life and that of the communities in general. However, there have been shortcomings in its implementation, as they are not equally accessible to all farmers, always benefiting the largest ones (p. 77-87).

Conclusions

It was analyzed that, according to the perception that officials have about public policies, there is a greater lack of knowledge of which currently govern, so the implementation would be beneficial for the management of agricultural industrialization in the district of Motupe, which is significant, in the sense that currently, the policies do not respond to the real needs of the agro-industrial sector. Hence, it fails to improve the conditions in which it is found.

The implementation of territorial policies in the agroindustry of the district of Motupe has an important benefit since there are public policies. However, they are not in line with the needs of the sector under study and taking into account that it is a district with a greater impact on the agroindustry, it should have legal guidelines and a positive impact.

The public policies currently in place for the agroindustrial sector in the Department of Lambayeque are not well defined by the authorities, or at least they are not efficiently aware of their purpose. Therefore, it is essential to address the policies so that they achieve successful results adequately, and the companies in this sector can rely on strengthened regulations.

The analysis shows that the current situation of the agroindustrial sector in the district of Motupe is worrisome because, in the last five years, no public policies have been designed to benefit this sector, and if they do exist, they are distorted and do not allow for improvements. It is also a serious problem that the authorities in charge of the agroindustrial sector do not know the policies that exist or were previously in place to provide input on their benefits before the possible implementation of new regulations.

References

- Arias, M. y Preciado, M. (2016). Paro Nacional Agrario: paradojas de la acción política para el cambio social. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 54 (5), p. 107-123. <http://web.b.ebscohost.com/ehost/pdfviewer/pdfviewer?vid=1&sid=f13e4f5d-4cc5-4e54-aaa7-08390fe45779%40pdc-v-sessmgr05>
- Banco Central de Reserva del Perú. (2020). Notas de estudio del BCRP. <https://www.bcrp.gob.pe/docs/Publicaciones/Notas-Estudios/2020/nota-de-estudios-38-2020.pdf>
- Bula, A. (2020). Importancia de la agricultura en el desarrollo socio-económico. Universidad Nacional de Rosario. <https://observatorio.unr.edu.ar/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Importancia-de-la-agricultura-en-el-desarrollo-socio-econ% C3% B3mico.pdf>
- Castillo Santa María, B., Larico, N.; y Moreno, A. (2020), <http://journals.cincader.org/index.php/sej/article/view/126/99>. *Revista de Ciencias e Ingeniería*, 4(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.32829/sej.v4i1.126>
- Castillo, B.; Carhuanchu, M. I. M.; & Moreno S, R. A. (2020), Políticas en la agricultura familiar, Cañete-2018. *INNOVA Research Journal*, 5(1), 232 - 247. doi:10.33890/Innova. vs.2020.1169
- Castillo, M., Villanueva, C., Moreno, R. y Agüero, H. (2020). Política nacional agraria en el Perú: Efectividad de los enfoques de gestión pública. *Revista Venezolana de Gerencia*, 25(89), 75-99. <https://www.redalyc.org/jatsRepo/290/29062641005/html/index.html>
- Caron, P., Ferrero, G., Nabarro, D., Hainzlin, E., Guillou, M., Andersen, I., Verburg, G. (2018). Food systems for sustainable development: proposals for a profound four-part

- transformation. *Agronomy for sustainable development*, 38(41), 1 - 12. Obtenido de <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-018-0519-1>
- Elver, H. (2018), *Human Rights Baed Approach to Sustainable Agricultural Policies and Food Security*. Springer Link. Obtenido de https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00758-4_17
- Hecló, H., Y Wildavsky, A. (1981). *The Prívate Government of Public Money* (1.a ed.1974), Macmillan, Londres
- Hernández, R. (2014). *Metodología de la investigación*. México D.F., México: McGraw- Hill.
- Huacchillo, L., Torres, N., y Ramos, E. (2020). *Inversión pública: factor contribuyente al crecimiento y emprendimiento empresarial la inversión pública: factor contribuyente para el crecimiento y emprendimiento empresarial*. Ha Científico de la Universidad de Cienfuegos. Volumen 12, Número 2.
file:///C:/Users/Admin/Downloads/La%20Inversion%20P%C3%BAblica.%20Factor%20Contribuyente%20Para%20El%20Crecimiento%20Y%20Emprendimiento.%20TADUCIDO_090604.pdf
- Isern, M. y Galati, E. (2015). *Epistemología*. <https://fcagr.unr.edu.ar/?p=6144>
- Mény, y Thoenig, J. (1992). *Las políticas públicas y teorías del Estado*. Documentación administrativa, 25 (4). Barcelona: Ariel.
- Muller, P. (2002). *Las Políticas Públicas*. Bogotá Colombia.: Universidad Externado de Colombia.
- Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Agricultura y la Alimentación. (2019). *El estado mundial de la agricultura y la alimentación. Progresos en la lucha contra la pérdida y el desperdicio de alimentos*. Roma. <https://www.fao.org/3/ca6030es/ca6030es.pdf>
- Organización de las Naciones Unidas. (2020). *La agenda 2030 y los objetivos de desarrollo sostenible. Una oportunidad para América Latina y el Caribe*. Cepal. https://repositorio.cepal.org/bitstream/handle/11362/40155/24/S1801141_es.pdf
- Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Agricultura y la Alimentación. (2019). *El estado mundial de la agricultura y la alimentación. Progresos en la lucha contra la pérdida y el desperdicio de alimentos*. Roma. <https://www.fao.org/3/ca6030es/ca6030es.pdf>
- Vargas, J., Barrantes, G., y Wong, L. (2022). *Public policies and agrarian development in Peru: A strategic planning approach*. *Revista Latinoamericana de Difusión Científica* Volumen 4 – Número 7.
<https://difusioncientifica.info/index.php/difusioncientifica/article/view/67/128>
- Vega, C., Paredes, M. y Almedida, A. (2018). *Desigualdades y crisis reproductiva tras el terremoto en la costa ecuatoriana. Estrategias familiares ante el modelo de desarrollo y trabajo extractivo*. *Revista de Antropología Iberoamericana*, 14 (2), p.323-350. <http://web.b.ebscohost.com/ehost/pdfviewer/pdfviewer?vid=1&sid=c9b0bda9-8e9f-45b1-97b7-b7d55ee26ce1%40pdc-v-sessmgr04>
- Velásquez, J., Suarez, J. y Ramírez, B. (2020). *Percepción y análisis de las políticas públicas de la producción de maíz en el centro oriente de Puebla, México*. *Cuadernos de desarrollo rural*, 17 (6), pp. 1-16.
<https://revistas.javeriana.edu.co/index.php/desarrolloRural/article/view/27034>
- Ziegler, S; Arias Segura, J; Bosio, M; Camacho, K. 2020. *Conectividad rural en América Latina y el Caribe: un puente al desarrollo sostenible en tiempos de pandemia* (en línea). San José, Costa Rica, IICA. 119 p.
<https://repositorio.iica.int/bitstream/handle/11324/12896/BVE20108887e.pdf?sequence=1%7B%5C%7DDisAllowed=y>